

CLASSIFYING LANGUISHING FOLK AND TRIBAL ARTS OF INDIA AS ROUT TO MORE RESPONSIVE SURVIVAL STRATEGY: A CONCEPTUAL NOTE

Dr. Hitaishi Singh,
Associate Professor, Home Science,
R.C.A. Girl's P.G. College, Mathura.
e-mail- singhitaishi@yahoo.co.in

ABSTRACT

India has a long-embedded tradition of beautiful folk and tribal arts. Many of these still exist, whereas many flourished and many perished with the time. Art has always been an integral part of the native people of this subcontinent from pre-historic era to the present times. One can find ample evidence from rock paintings of Bagh and Bhimbetka to the frescos of Ajanta caves and murals of Kerala along with plethora of tribal and miniature art forms. You name a place in the country and you will find number of such forms scattered across that area. However, it was observed that there is a great deal of confusion on the basic definition, related concepts which overlaps the components, understanding and classification of tribal arts and folk arts and its various derivatives. It was also seen that many of such art forms are on the verge of extinction and are liable to languish in no time if not given proper protection. Therefore, firstly at conceptual level the paper has attempted to identify the difference between these terms. Secondly, it has come up with the clear-cut classification of tribal arts and folk arts individually that can be used for further researches. Finally, it has given few suggestions for further classifications based on survival levels and act accordingly to protect them from extinction as these are not only a part of our intrinsic culture but also their protection and promotion can serve as source of livelihood for many practicing communities. Overall, the paper provides multiple solution to the policy and strategy designers that can play vital role in the protection, promotion and socio-economic development and sustenance of folk and tribal arts of India and its practitioners.

Key Words: Folk art, Tribal Art, Languishing Arts, Cultural Heritage, survival strategy.

A. Introduction

India, as multi- cultural and multi-ethnic society is a home to as many as 700 tribal communities (Census of India, 2001).² Simultaneously, it is a rural economy-based culture which is particularly known for its rich legacy and repository of versatile folk and tribal arts. "It's folk and tribal arts are representation of its cultural wealth and vibrancy. These arts are visual arts for example paintings depicting their lifestyle, tradition and culture. They have a set of belief system that allows them to interpret things in their own native ways and

this influences them even in their art. Further, here Puranic Gods and legends are often changed into contemporary manner” (Smith 2006).⁸ Evidences of these arts forms can also be seen in various archaeological remains found at excavation sites in a variety of forms and materials.

Evolution of these art forms rests into their basic ethos, life styles and their surrounding eco- system. Further, a wide diversity is seen in terms of communities and casts with equal number of variations of art as form of expression amongst these diverse folk groups from north to down south and from far east to west. Every community and its geographical surroundings have a very distinctive environment producing local material, themes, symbolism and developing techniques for producing art works. Even with in the art form each artist has its own style, composition, use of lines and shapes or selection of colours and motifs with in the given periphery of that art form. Perhaps this is the basis of their simplicity yet versatility, vibrant nature and aesthetics.

“Tribal and folk-art forms are creative expression of people who live in harmony with nature and are passed on to the next generation”.⁶

Existing definitions of folk and tribal arts generally mixes the two, as Smith (2006) says, **“Tribal and folk art belong to the section of people who belong to different social groups and it has a native flavour”.⁸**

“Tribal and folk art is related to fairs, festivals, local deities, fantasy in their representation. Indian art cannot do away with this section that has a regional and a mystic aura in it. Nomadic way of life is also an integral part of the tribal and folk art”. (Das 1979).³

In current times many of these art forms have been recognized as independent art forms but a good number of them are struggling to survive. Further, review of related researches showed an overlap between terms when it comes to differentiate between folk and tribal art. **Therefore, the current study was devised with two purposes-**

1. To identify the difference between folk arts and tribal arts and give a proper definition of both.
2. To provide classifications of folk and tribal arts individually that can be used for further researches at conceptual level and give suggestions for better responsive classifications for future policy and protective actions for their survival.

Methodology adopted was purely based on secondary sources- literature, reports, Census data, past researches, etc. and few field trips made for the purpose. However, no single research focused on making distinction and classification of these two art forms in

Indian context was found. Few field trips were made and observations made were jotted down and accordingly the present conceptual paper was developed.

B. Difference between folk and tribal art

There is a distinct difference between tribal communities and folk communities and hence there is difference between folk and tribal arts in its genre, medium, themes and way of representation and expression. Each has special features typical to that particular group.

Approximately 92 percent of this total tribal population of India resides in hilly, dry and forested areas and they account 8.2 percent of the total population of the country. When we talk about rural (folk) population, it comprises of 72.4 percent of the total population of India and since majority of scheduled tribes live in rural areas and their population is 10.42 percent of the total rural population (Census of India, 2001),² many people get confused between folk and tribal population and their arts. As a result, there is an overlap of tribal and folk arts while classifying them. Most of the tribal arts have some connection with their worship rituals and totems. At the same time, they have their own set of kinship ties, and they fall comparatively under earlier level of social development of civilization hence, they and their art forms are different from folk and other native arts forms. However, tribal and folk, both types of arts are essentially a group art than individual arts to a large extent but some of the categories of folk arts may be classified as individual artist-based arts. The case of later on added miniature art is one example. Here each person may develop a different level of proficiency due to individual differences in ability and dedication towards the art form. Thus, there is a need to understand each one in relation to the other very clearly. For the purpose, let us take them one by one.

1. Tribal Art

Before defining tribal art it is important to understand the nature and characteristics that defines their practitioners – the tribals.

“A group of native inhabitants that are clubbed under a schedule on the basis of criteria given bellow as per Indian law are officially referred as scheduled tribes. Consequently, all visual (painted) art forms practiced by these tribes is defined as Tribal Art”

“The criteria that are followed for identification and categorizing Scheduled Tribes (ST) in India are -

- a. Indicative of primitive traits.**
- b. Distinctive culture.**
- c. Geographical isolation.**

d. Shyness of contact with the communities at large.

e. Backwardness.”²

Each State of India has its own group of scheduled tribes falling under the category classified on the basis of above indicators. Each of these ethnic groups resides in a particular geographical area and accordingly they have their own language if not script, own ways of dressing, food, life style, cultural practices and arts and craft. These features make them different. For example- *Pithora* paintings of *Rathwa* tribe of Gujarat it is entirely different from the paintings of *Warli* tribe^{1,4,11} of Gujarat and Maharashtra or *Saura* tribe of Orissa.

The tribal art forms, be shaped by religious motifs or as depiction of their part of living, consists off simple linear or geometrical expressions without any distinction of boundaries of other forms of fine or applied art and thus it is part of their integral life. It is also termed as ethnographic art or pre-historic art⁵ by some experts but in some cases, this definition does not fit. Therefore, in Indian context the indicators decided by the Ministry of tribal affairs, also given as a part of census report, mentioned above were found to be the most suitable criteria for identification of tribes and further their visual arts.

Classification of Tribal Arts-

Classification of tribal arts on the basis of concentration of population in different parts of the country-

For this purpose, state wise tribal atlas of the country was taken as refence point and the list of state wise tribes was referred to avoid any duplicity and misconceptions. These were further divided as per their population percentage and accordingly classified into 05 categories. These are -

- a. Art forms practiced by scheduled tribes with more than 75 percent population- **Flourishing properly and under Extremely Protected Category of Sustenance** – Examples are Gond art, Warli Art.
- b. Art forms practiced by scheduled tribes with more than 50 percent but less than 75 percent population- **Flourishing and under Protected Category of Sustenance.** Example- Santhal art.
- c. Art forms practiced by scheduled tribes with more than 25 percent but less than 50 percent population- **Not Flourishing properly but fall under the Category of Average Sustenance** - Example- Saura art.

- d. Art forms practiced by scheduled tribes with more than 10 percent but less than 25 percent population- **Not so Vulnerable and under Endangered Category of Sustenance.** Example- Sohrai.
- e. Art forms practiced by scheduled tribes with less than 10 percent population- **Highly Vulnerable and under Extremely Endangered Category of Sustenance.** Example- Art form practiced by Onge tribe of Andaman Island.

2. Folk Arts:

Though tribes are mostly inhabitant of rural areas but folk arts are non- tribal in nature and likewise the practitioners of folk arts are also different from the practitioners of tribal art. These are people who do not fall under the official category of scheduled tribes of the country but reside essentially in rural areas. Probably Mithila (Madhubani-means honey forest) is one of the most common genres of Indian folk paintings in literal sense” that caught the attention towards this aspect of painted arts.¹⁰

Merriam Webster has defined folk arts as **“the traditional decorative or utilitarian art of the people that is often an expression of community life and is distinguished for academic or self-conscious or cosmopolitan expression.”**⁷

However, the following may be considered as more comprehensive definition, **“The term folk, thus, encompasses all the people living in a particular area, having some specific and constant traits and awareness & consciousness towards preserving their cultural heritage. They are essentially from rural background and are passed on from one to the next generation”**. Folk arts in Indian context is an art practiced by these rural folks from a long period of time which may be as old as the civilization. They may be classified under several type of categories discussed in following pages.

Some western experts define folk art as the art practiced by aboriginal civilization or by peasants or other working-class people. Its first and foremost specific feature is that it is functional as well as decorative rather being having just a visual appeal. However, there may be certain broader yet much specific criteria for classifying Indian folk arts as the very nature in terms of antiquity, diversity, socio- cultural structures, and ethos of Indian folk life is different from other countries. Their art forms come naturally yet generally with some purpose.

Folk arts have been evolved from various sources of folk and daily lives and surrounding environment of rural folks and advanced as a variety of folk-art forms. It is very difficult to categorize these folk-art forms but an attempt is made to keep the

classification as lucid and specific as possible. However, there are several places where minor overlapping has taken place as few of the art forms fall in more than one category. Folk arts may be classified in three ways-

1. **A detailed classification of folk arts on the basis of its source of origin and type of peoples' participation -**

a. **Folk arts forms practiced by a particular community of the area-**

In India there are several communities that practice a particular art form as community art. Some of them such as *Mata- ne- pachedi* from Gujarat has an interesting story behind for its development as an art form. Another worth noting example is Bengal *patachitra* or *pata* practiced by *Chitrakar* community of Naya, Medinipur, West Bengal. Interestingly, these Chitrakars belong to Hindu and Muslim both the communities and make scrolls on the themes of important events from their social life and Hindu religious stories and epics irrespective of their religion. Likewise, *Deewaru* community from Shivmoga, Karnataka practices *Chittara* art which creates magic with simple lines.

b. **Folk arts forms practiced by most people of the area as their routine practice and as part of their life style-**

Some of the folk arts reflect their origin in certain specific community and on the other hand others may have its origin as an art form practiced by most people of area irrespective of any particular community or caste division as such. These are used for both, ornamentation and religious & ritualistic purpose as part of life style of people. The most appropriate example is Madhubani art and its variations like *Kachni- Bharni*, *Tantrik Madhubani* and *Kohbar* from Mithila region of Bihar^{9,10,12} and most of the floor ornamentation methods such as *Rangoli*, *Alpana*, *Kolam* or *Aipan* fall under this category.

2. **A detailed classification of folk arts on the basis of its source of origin-**

a. **Folk arts forms having purely religious roots or temple tradition -**

This type of art forms encompasses those ones which have been practiced initially strictly as a religious ritualistic art originating from temple tradition since antiquity. Sanjhi art originated from Mathura, Uttar Pradesh that further spread to parts of Rajasthan and Gujarat, *Kalamezhuthu* and Murals of temples of Kerala and *Kalamkari* originating from Shrikalahasti, Patachitra of Raghurajpur, Orissa or *Pichwais* of Nathdwara, Rajasthan are few examples of this category of folk art. These art forms are highly ornamental yet a fine blend

of mature realistic depiction with native influence on characterization of flora fauna, ornamentation and figures.

b. Folk arts forms originated from more fine and artistically mature forms of visual art and folk art forms-

Further, another of art form which is added to the category of folk art comparatively in later period belong to finer art category requiring extremely developed artistic skills are miniature paintings, manuscript paintings and geometrical paintings and frescos. Miniature paintings from Rajasthan, Punjab, Garhwal hills, Himachal Pradesh, South India and manuscript paintings from Assam or *Jain* manuscripts, Tanjore and Mysore paintings, etc. are fine example of these folk-art forms. These paintings are characterised by their local influence on characterization of human and animal figures and the surrounding composition but also have very fine and mature workmanship. This also include beautiful geometrical art and frescos done mainly in the buildings of Jaipur Shekhawati, and, Udaipur of Rajasthan.

3. A detailed classification of folk arts on the basis of its purpose of making of folk arts-

a. Folk arts forms used traditionally as a tool of communication and message giving purpose-

This is one category under which many folk-art forms from other categories may fall. Various folk-art forms were being used in older times in village or community as a source of communication through story telling approach or folk theatre approach for disseminating moral teaching messages. In modern times they are utilised for making people aware about many social and health issues. These folk-art methods are used in multiple mediums and utilizes variety of materials.

Some of the examples of folk arts used for communication purpose are *Kavad* painting and *Phad* painting of Rajasthan, *Tholu bomalatta* leather puppet paintings evolved from shadow puppet theatre, Andhra Pradesh, *Cherriyal mask* painting and *Cherriyal Nakashi* (scroll) paintings of Telangana, mask making and painting of Chau dance, *Paitkar* paintings of scroll used as visual narrative of stories of *Ramayana* and *Mahabharata* done by people from Amadubi village of Dalbhumgarh area, Jharkhand, etc.

b. Expression and representation of themselves and their eco-system-

This category is based on the Hindu philosophy of “Swabhivyakti” and Swantah Sukhaye”-the art form practiced for self-expression and self-satisfaction. The folk art that is used as simple expression of their sentiments, emotions, day- to- day life, daily lives, belief systems, etc. of folk people. Somewhere, in most cases of folk arts this philosophy is soul and is common to all other art forms too. It is the main objective for as well as resultant of practicing any such art.

c. Folk arts forms serving purely utilitarian purpose along with attributing to ornamentation of the product-

Though most folk-art forms initially evolved as floor or wall decoration but there is a set of artistic folk arts that were evolved purely as to be used on utility articles. Some of such art forms are Kashmiri paintings on papier-mâché products, paintings on board games and Ganjifa cards, etc.

d. Cultural purpose-

Another form that is frequently seen is use of these art forms for decorating items of daily use or items used for certain customary or ceremonial purposes. This includes several folk-art forms. *Kohbar*, *Satiya* and *Chauk Poorna* from Uttar Pradesh and *Kohbar* of Bihar, *Mandana* from Rajasthan and Madhya Pradesh may be considered to name from this category.

e. Recreational purpose-

Folk theatre performing masks painting and traditional puppets or *Ganjifa* game, etc. comes under this category.

A. Suggestions

Finally, it was observed that if the population of a particular tribal or folk group practicing a particular folk art is high, it is not an assurance that its arts will also survive and flourish well.

Some important facts in this regard observed by the researcher are-

- a. Many of these folk and tribal arts could flourish and thus be saved due to timely intervention by some kind of patronage or economic intervention initiative. Many art connoisseurs, patrons or the institutions recognized them well on time and took initiatives to protect the art forms but the artists too. This not only gave international level recognition to these folk and tribal art but also led to the diversification of folk art into multiple utility-based articles that kept the market demand growing and

hence the folk art survived, grew and flourished. Two peculiar examples of each are - *Madhubani* folk art, and *Sanjhi* Stencil cut and tribal arts *Worli* tribal art and *Gond* tribal art.

- b. Many of folk and tribal arts that still exist but only few-one or two-practicing families are left. They are, therefore, on the verge of extinction such as Cherriyal scrolls or Rathwa tribal art and are considered as languishing folk and tribal arts.
- c. The third category covers those tribal and folk art that were languished completely but in last few years, they have been revived. Some of them are thriving ones. few others are growing at optimistic pace.
- d. But there is a fourth category too. These were those unfortunate ones which perished with the passage of time.

Therefore, some pragmatically workable, feasibly applicable, empirically correct criteria for making categories and classifying tribal and folk art have been suggested with the idea of providing better protection and survival strategy. These are given as suggestion as under-

- a. Classification of folk and tribal arts individually in term of their level of survival.
- b. Classification of tribal and folk arts on the basis of _number of types of tribe wise data practicing particular tribal art with its population in their respective areas which may be divided state wise or zone wise.
- c. Classification of tribal and folk arts on the basis of _number of types of folk groups wise data practicing particular folk art with its population in their respective areas which may be divided state wise or zone wise.
- d. Another suggestion is that these may also be broadly classified on the basis of popularity or forms of presentation.

The first type of suggested classification is suggested as under.

Classification of folk and tribal arts individually in term of their level of survival-

Existence of tribal and folk arts of different tribal and folk groups as per the following levels of survival be identified and then further divide them state wise or zone wise for better responding policies and strategies-

a. For Tribal Arts

- i. Tribal arts that have already languished and need revival, protection and promotion.
- ii. Tribal arts that are languishing and need immediate protection and promotion.

- iii. Tribal arts that were languished but revived and now need protection and promotion.
- iv. Tribal arts that are already protected and promoted well so no fear of being languished.
- b. **For Folk Arts-**
 - v. Folk arts that have already languished and need revival, protection and promotion.
 - vi. Folk arts that are languishing and need immediate protection and promotion.
 - vii. Folk arts that were languished but revived and now need protection and promotion.
 - viii. Folk arts that are already protected and promoted well so no fear of being languished.

B. Conclusion

Country's native people and the folk and tribal paintings made by them are custodian of our rich heritage, enriched artistry and a visual documentation of our glorious past which needs to be revived, protected, promoted and continued.

In nutshell, serious and systematic efforts are needed and the paper has looked into the issue with various angles keeping several important key points in mind. Hope it will be useful for the future researchers, policy makers and strategy designers. Very little has been done looking at this vast wealth scattered across land and a lot needs to be done.

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